

STATE AND LAW

THE EVOLUTION OF THE CONCEPT OF PUBLIC SAFETY: FROM PHYSICAL PROTECTION TO GLOBAL SECURITY

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Abstract

Public safety is essential for the stability and well-being of any society, involving the protection of citizens from threats to social order and physical integrity. Over time, the concept of public safety has evolved from physical defense against criminals to a broader vision, encompassing economic, social, health, and political aspects. Institutions responsible for public safety, such as the police, gendarmerie, judiciary, and emergency services, play a crucial role in maintaining order and protecting citizens. Moreover, public safety addresses various issues, from physical and economic safety to cybersecurity and social security. Modern challenges such as terrorism, cybercrime, and climate change complicate the maintenance of safety. Active citizen involvement, through civic education and cooperation with authorities, is essential for the long-term success of public safety efforts.

Keywords: Public safety, Citizen protection, Social order, National security, Modern crises, Crime prevention.

1. The Concept of Public Safety

Public safety is a fundamental element in any society, directly linked to collective stability and well-being. This concept involves the protection of citizens from threats that affect social order and physical integrity, as well as maintaining a safe and peaceful environment in which individuals can develop harmoniously. The following sections will explore the significance of public safety, its historical evolution, the role of institutions in its maintenance, and current challenges in ensuring security in an increasingly complex world.

In Romania, public safety is regulated by a solid legislative framework consisting of laws, regulations, and national strategies aimed at protecting citizens and communities from threats to social order, individual security, and territorial integrity. The concept of public safety extends beyond crime prevention, including a comprehensive set of measures to ensure social, economic, and political stability.

In Romanian law, public safety is regulated by a series of fundamental laws and normative acts that clearly define the roles and responsibilities of state institutions. These include:

- The Constitution of Romania: The Constitution guarantees citizens the right to security and protection, establishing the legal basis for state intervention in maintaining public order and protecting fundamental rights. Article 22 ensures the right to life and physical and mental integrity, while Article 23 enshrines the inviolability of individual liberty.
- Law No. 218/2002 on the Organization and Functioning of the Romanian Police: This law governs the role of the Romanian Police in maintaining public safety and social order. The police are tasked with preventing and combating crime, responding to emergencies, and protecting citizens from various threats. The law also details the duties of local police, emphasizing collaboration with the community.

- Law No. 550/2004 on the Organization and Functioning of the Romanian Gendarmerie: The Gendarmerie plays a crucial role in maintaining public order, intervening in cases of social unrest, violent protests, and other threats that require a militarized force. The law establishes the structure and operation of the Gendarmerie, including in rural areas and high-risk zones.

- Law No. 51/1991 on National Security: This law regulates measures for protecting national security, including preventing and combating threats to the state. Public safety and national security are closely linked, as any threat to the state can directly affect the population.

- The Criminal Code: The Criminal Code establishes penalties for offenses that endanger public safety, including acts of terrorism, drug trafficking, and organized crime, contributing to the maintenance of social order and security.

- Emergency Ordinance No. 195/2002 on Road Traffic: This ordinance regulates road safety, an important aspect of public safety. It provides measures for ensuring traffic order, preventing accidents, and sanctioning violations of traffic rules.

- Law No. 272/2004 on the Protection and Promotion of Children's Rights: Public safety also includes the protection of vulnerable groups, such as children. This law provides special measures for protecting children in situations of risk, such as abuse or exploitation, contributing to the creation of a safe environment for them.

In conclusion, public safety represents an essential pillar in Romanian legislation, aiming to protect citizens from crimes, health risks, environmental hazards, and other threats. The Romanian legal and institutional system adopts an integrated approach to maintaining public order and stability in the face of modern challenges.

2. The Evolution of the Public Safety Concept

In the past, the concept of public safety was much narrower, focusing primarily on physical protection against immediate threats such as thieves, criminals, or external attacks. Especially in earlier historical periods, public safety was associated with the defense of cities and regions against armed bands or with maintaining order through local police structures or military units. As societies urbanized and modernized in the 19th century, this concept expanded to include not only crime prevention and control but also improving the quality of life through regulations and social policies.

As societies evolved, public safety became a more complex concept, integrating economic, social, health, and political dimensions. For example, in the 19th and 20th centuries, the rise of urban crime such as robberies, fraud, and labor revolts led to the need for more robust structures to maintain public order and security.

The concept of public safety is fundamental to maintaining order, stability, and prosperity within a society. The application of this concept is indispensable for several key reasons:

1. Protecting Life and Property

One of the main objectives of public safety is to protect citizens and their property. Without an organized framework for public safety, individuals would constantly be exposed to risks of violence, crime, or accidents, which would destabilize communities and severely impact the normal functioning of society.

2. Maintaining Order and Social Peace

Public safety plays a crucial role in ensuring respect for laws and preventing social unrest. Maintaining order guarantees a stable environment where citizens can carry out their daily activities without fear of conflict, crime, or disorder.

3. Crisis Prevention and Management

Modern threats such as terrorism, natural disasters, epidemics, or cybercrime require a solid public safety structure to anticipate and efficiently manage such crises. Prevention and rapid response are essential to minimize the impact of these threats on the population and infrastructure.

4. Strengthening Trust in Institutions

A well-organized and efficient public safety system increases citizens' trust in state institutions. People need to have the assurance that the government and authorities are capable of providing protection, and this sense of safety contributes to social cohesion and political stability.

5. Stimulating Economic Development

In the absence of public safety, investments and economic development would be severely affected. In an insecure environment, companies hesitate to invest, leading to economic stagnation. A safe community attracts investments, promotes economic development, and contributes to overall prosperity.

6. Promoting Social Progress and Community Cohesion

Public safety is not limited to physical protection but also includes social aspects. Reducing inequalities and promoting a fair environment are key elements in ensuring social cohesion. Creating a safe environment

supports a united and progressive community, where individuals collaborate for the common good.

3. Why the Public Safety Concept is Less Utilized

The concept of public safety continues to be used and remains highly relevant in contemporary society, but it may sometimes seem less explicitly mentioned because it has become deeply integrated into the functioning of institutions and daily life. However, there are several reasons why the term may seem less visible in certain contexts:

Over time, the concept of public safety has expanded to include multiple dimensions, such as cybersecurity, public health, environmental protection, and economic security. These areas have become independent topics of discussion but are an integral part of public safety. In a modern world, these branches have gained their own identity, and the general term "public safety" may seem less used because the sectors contributing to it have diversified.

The concept of public safety has often been replaced in common usage by specific terms that more precisely define the various aspects of security. For example:

- Cybersecurity refers to protection against digital threats.
- National security includes protection against terrorist threats and external attacks.
- Public health refers to the prevention and management of diseases, a crucial dimension of public safety.
- Road safety refers to measures that ensure the reduction of traffic accidents.

Using specific terms makes discussions more precise, context-appropriate, and easier for the general public to understand.

The concept of security in general has evolved, and "public safety" can be perceived as part of a broader security concept. Institutions and authorities now use terms such as national security, collective security, or global security, which integrate the idea of public safety but at a broader level to reflect the complex and interdependent threats of the contemporary world.

In recent years, the focus has shifted from reactive public safety (maintaining order after a crisis) to a proactive approach, focused on prevention and resilience. Government authorities and international institutions emphasize the need to prevent threats before they materialize and to prepare society to respond effectively to crises, whether they are cyber, health-related, or natural disasters.

With globalization, public safety threats have become more complex and more challenging to manage at strictly national or local levels. Issues such as climate change, migration, international terrorism, and cyberattacks require international cooperation and a multilateral approach. In this context, public safety is integrated into a broader global security framework and is not always discussed in isolated terms.

In many countries, public safety concepts and measures have become an integral part of the daily activities of governments and local authorities. Thus, even though the term is not constantly mentioned, it is

embedded in the current activities of institutions that ensure the order, health, and well-being of communities.

In many countries, the concepts and measures related to public safety have become an integral part of the daily activities of governments and local authorities. Thus, even though the term may not be constantly mentioned, it is embedded in the current work of institutions that ensure the order, health, and well-being of communities.

Although the term "public safety" may seem to be used less frequently in certain contexts, the concept remains equally important. In reality, public safety is omnipresent and is integrated into various sectors and policies that protect individuals and societies from modern and complex threats. Adapting the language to specific fields and challenges makes public safety better understood and applied in practice.

The concept of public safety is essential for maintaining order, stability, and well-being in a society. Its application is necessary for several fundamental reasons:

1. *Protecting Life and Property*

The primary goal of public safety is to protect citizens and their belongings. Without an organized framework for public safety, individuals would face constant risks of violence, crime, or accidents, which would destabilize communities and significantly impact the normal functioning of society.

2. *Maintaining Order and Social Peace*

Public safety ensures the enforcement of laws and prevents social unrest. By maintaining order, a stable environment is created where citizens can go about their daily activities without fear of conflicts, crimes, or disorder.

3. *Crisis Prevention and Management*

Modern threats like terrorism, natural disasters, epidemics, or cybercrime require a strong public safety structure to anticipate and efficiently manage such crises. Prevention and rapid response are crucial to minimizing the impact of these threats on the population and infrastructure.

4. *Building Trust in Institutions*

A well-organized and efficient public safety system increases citizens' trust in state institutions. People need to know that the government and authorities can protect them, and this sense of safety contributes to social cohesion and political stability.

5. *Promoting Economic Development*

Without public safety, investments and economic development would be severely impacted. In an insecure environment, companies hesitate to invest, leading to economic stagnation. A safe community attracts investments, promotes economic development, and contributes to overall prosperity.

6. *Fostering Social Progress and Community Cohesion*

Public safety is not limited to physical protection; it also includes social security. Reducing inequalities and promoting a fair environment are key factors in ensuring social cohesion. Creating a safe environment supports a united and progressive community where individuals collaborate for the common good.

4. Institutions Responsible for Public Safety

Public safety is ensured by a network of government institutions, each with specific roles and responsibilities in maintaining order and protecting citizens. These institutions play a vital role in protecting citizens and ensuring order and stability in society.

In Romania, the main structures involved in maintaining public safety include:

1. *The Romanian Police*

○ Role and responsibilities: The Romanian Police is the primary body responsible for maintaining public order and citizen safety. It focuses on preventing and combating crime, managing emergency situations, ensuring road safety, and protecting both public and private property.

○ Specialized structures: The police are divided into several departments, such as the traffic police, judicial police, forensic services, and community policing, which work together to ensure a safe environment for communities.

2. *The Romanian Gendarmerie*

○ Role and responsibilities: The Gendarmerie is a militarized force tasked with maintaining public order, especially in crisis situations, violent protests, or other social disturbances. It also protects strategic objectives and cooperates with other institutions to ensure security.

○ Specialized interventions: The Gendarmerie intervenes in less accessible or rural areas and plays an important role in environmental protection and border security.

3. *The Romanian Intelligence Service (SRI)*

○ Role and responsibilities: SRI focuses on preventing and combating threats to national security, such as terrorism, espionage, and organized crime. Although not directly involved in day-to-day public safety, its activities protect citizens by identifying and neutralizing major risks.

○ Surveillance and collaboration: SRI conducts monitoring and analysis activities, collaborating with other agencies to prevent threats that could affect public safety.

4. *Border Police:*

○ Role and responsibilities: It ensures security at Romania's borders by preventing and combating cross-border crimes such as smuggling, human trafficking, and illegal migration. The Border Police contributes to national security by strictly controlling the flow of people and goods.

○ International cooperation: The Border Police cooperates with European and international organizations to effectively manage border security and prevent cross-border crimes.

5. *The General Inspectorate for Emergency Situations (ISU):*

○ Role and responsibilities: ISU intervenes in case of fires, earthquakes, floods, and other natural or industrial disasters. They are also responsible for preventing such situations and saving lives and property in emergencies.

○ Prevention and rescue: ISU conducts disaster prevention activities and educates the population about safety measures in such situations.

6. *The Ministry of Internal Affairs (MAI):*

- Role and responsibilities: MAI oversees all activities related to public safety through its subordinate institutions, such as the Police, Gendarmerie, ISU, and Border Police. It also develops national policies and strategies for public order and national security.

- Coordination: The Ministry coordinates public order institutions and ensures effective collaboration between them and other authorities.

7. *The Judicial System (Prosecutor's Office and Courts of Law):*

- Role and responsibilities: The judicial system enforces laws and sanctions criminals, contributing to maintaining social order and public safety. The courts play a crucial role in fighting crime through fair and transparent trials.

- Collaboration with law enforcement: Prosecutors work closely with the Police and other law enforcement agencies in investigating and prosecuting crimes.

8. *The National Anti-Drug Agency (ANA):*

- Role and responsibilities: ANA is responsible for preventing and combating drug trafficking and substance abuse. The agency carries out prevention and education campaigns in schools and vulnerable communities.

- Preventive activities: ANA collaborates with other institutions to limit the spread of drug use and its impact on society.

9. *Local Authorities:*

- Role and responsibilities: Local authorities contribute to public safety by working with Local Police and other agencies to maintain order in communities. They implement measures tailored to local needs and manage crime prevention initiatives.

- Support in communities: They conduct awareness campaigns and social programs to ensure a safe and protected environment for citizens.

10. *The Directorate for Investigating Organized Crime and Terrorism (DIICOT):*

- Role and responsibilities: DIICOT investigates and combats organized crime and terrorism, with extensive competence in areas such as drug trafficking, human trafficking, arms trafficking, and cyber fraud. The Directorate plays a crucial role in maintaining national public safety.

- International cooperation: DIICOT collaborates with other states and international organizations to counter transnational crime networks.

These institutions work collaboratively to maintain public safety and ensure a secure and stable environment for all citizens.

Institutions responsible for public safety in Romania have well-defined roles and collaborate to protect citizens and maintain social order. Each institution contributes through its competencies to the efficient management of modern risks and challenges, thus ensuring a safe environment for all.

5. **Areas of Public Safety**

Public safety is a complex and multidimensional concept that plays a central role in ensuring the stability and well-being of a society. This concept encompasses a range of interconnected areas that, together, contrib-

ute to protecting citizens and maintaining an environment of order and security. In an increasingly globalized and interdependent world, the challenges facing public safety are becoming more diverse, and effectively managing these threats is essential for the functioning of a modern society.

1. *Physical Safety*

Physical safety is one of the most fundamental and oldest dimensions of public safety, aimed at protecting citizens from violence, crime, and other forms of aggression. Typically, this type of safety is managed by law enforcement agencies and other institutions tasked with maintaining public order and responding quickly to any threat that could endanger individuals' physical integrity.

Over time, crime-fighting strategies have evolved from reactive responses to incidents to the implementation of prevention strategies. Authorities no longer just respond to critical situations but also adopt proactive measures, such as regularly patrolling risk-exposed areas, conducting awareness campaigns, and implementing community collaboration programs. These actions contribute to creating a safe and stable environment for all citizens.

Success in ensuring public safety largely depends on close cooperation between authorities and citizens. This cooperation facilitates both crime prevention and rapid intervention, while also strengthening trust between the public and law enforcement institutions. Active community involvement in identifying risks and threats thus becomes a key element in maintaining a climate of safety and stability.

2. *Economic Safety*

Economic safety is another essential area of public safety because a stable and functioning economy is crucial for maintaining order and social stability. People need access to jobs, decent wages, and opportunities for economic growth to feel secure and avoid engaging in illicit or violent activities due to a lack of alternatives.

Economic and financial institutions, together with governments, play a crucial role in protecting citizens from fraud, money laundering, tax evasion, and other economic crimes. Additionally, protection against poverty and economic insecurity through social assistance programs, education, and public health contributes to creating a safe and sustainable economic environment.

3. *Health and Food Safety*

An important aspect of public safety is protecting public health and ensuring the quality of food and water resources. In a globalized world where goods and people move rapidly from one region to another, public health becomes an essential area in ensuring the general safety of the population.

Epidemics, pandemics, and health crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, have shown how vulnerable a society can be to health threats. Protecting public health through disease prevention measures, ensuring access to healthcare services, and safeguarding food safety are essential to maintaining public safety.

4. *Cybersecurity*

With the development of technology and the increasing digitalization of daily life, cybersecurity has

become a major priority for governments and institutions. Cybercrime, such as hacking attacks, online fraud, identity theft, and compromising critical infrastructures, poses major threats to public safety.

Protecting critical infrastructure, such as financial, energy, and communication systems, is essential to prevent major disruptions in society's functioning. Additionally, safeguarding citizens' personal data and protecting it from cyberattacks are central elements of public safety in the digital age.

Governments, cybersecurity agencies, and private companies collaborate to develop solutions to prevent cyberattacks and to protect citizens and infrastructure from such threats. By forming rapid response teams for cyber incidents and educating the public on the importance of cybersecurity, society's overall protection can be improved.

5. Social Safety

Social safety refers to the stability and cohesion within a community. Creating a safe environment where individuals have access to resources, jobs, and social services is essential for preventing social unrest and conflicts. Economic and social inequalities can create tensions in communities, leading to revolts or increased crime.

Social programs that support education, health, housing, and social assistance contribute significantly to reducing social risks. Additionally, preventing social exclusion and promoting the integration of minorities and vulnerable groups are essential measures for ensuring social safety. Ensuring equal access to resources and opportunities for all citizens helps prevent social instability and promotes a safer and more united society.

6. Road safety

Road safety is another essential area of public safety, having a direct impact on the daily life of citizens. Traffic accidents are a major threat to people's lives and health, and prevention of these strict regulations, adequate infrastructure and road education is crucial. "In some states in the European Union, criminal legislation includes severe offenses regarding leaving the scene of an accident, with the aim of strengthening the liability of drivers and reducing the number of fatal road incidents" (Tical & Chiruta, 2019, p. 45).

Governments and local authorities are responsible for implementing measures to ensure road safety. These measures include proper road signage, the construction of modern infrastructure and campaigns to educate citizens about responsible traffic behavior. The traffic police also play a central role in monitoring and enforcing traffic laws, thus reducing the risks of accidents.

7. Environmental safety

Environmental protection is crucial for maintaining long-term public safety, given that climate change, pollution and ecosystem degradation threaten not only natural resources, but also the social and economic stability of affected regions. Extreme climate change may lead to an intensification of regional conflicts over access to natural resources, especially in already vulnerable areas.

Moreover, "lack of access to clean water and basic resources is a trigger for forced migration and international conflict" (Lavanya Rajamani, p. 87). In this context, the development of environmental protection policies and the sustainable use of resources are essential. Johnson points out, in *Sustainable Resource Management* (Harvard Press, 2020), that "implementing sustainable energy policies and protecting vulnerable ecosystems is the basis of long-term public safety" (p. 154).

8. Demographic safety

Demographic safety involves the proper management of population changes and their impact on public safety. Changes such as migration, population aging and rapid population growth in certain regions can cause economic and social tensions that affect overall stability. For example, "uncontrolled migration can disrupt the capacity of health and education systems in host countries, putting pressure on these infrastructures and creating social imbalance" (Smith, 2020, p. 58). Thus, these pressures can lead to social instability and conflict.

In order to maintain a social balance, it is necessary to implement effective policies that address these demographic transformations. "Managing migration requires structured integration programs that support both migration and host communities" (Johnson & Martinez, 2019, p. 45). At the same time, supporting young people in areas affected by unemployment and migration is crucial, because they can become or valuable resource for social stability if they are integrated into the community.

9. Legal security and citizens' rights

Public safety cannot exist without protection of the fundamental rights of citizens. An efficient, fair and accessible judicial system is essential for maintaining order and ensuring citizens' trust in state institutions. Legal certainty involves the application of laws in a fair and transparent manner, so that they are protected against abuses and violations of their rights.

The authorities must ensure that all citizens have access to a fair legal system that protects human rights and applies sanctions fairly in cases of crime. Also, preventing corruption and ensuring the integrity of the justice system are essential to maintaining public safety.

10. Security against terrorism and extremism

In an increasingly globalized and interconnected world, terrorism and extremism are major threats to public safety. Terrorist attacks can have a devastating impact on communities and destabilize societies. Preventing radicalization and countering extremist groups is essential to maintaining public safety.

Governments and international agencies work together to develop strategies to prevent terrorism, including by monitoring suspicious activities, preventing terrorist financing, and running programs to rehabilitate and reintegrate radicalized individuals.

Public safety is a vast and multidimensional concept that includes many interconnected fields, each essential to protecting citizens and maintaining social stability. From physical and economic security to cyber, health and environmental security, all these areas contribute to creating a safe and stable environment in

which individuals can live and thrive. In an increasingly complex and challenging world, collaboration between governments, institutions and citizens becomes essential to effectively respond to threats to public safety and to ensure the long-term well-being of society.

6. Contemporary challenges in the field of Public Safety

Today's public safety challenges are multiple and complex as the world becomes increasingly interconnected and new technologies, climate change, global migration and other emerging phenomena impact social and economic stability. In this context, the challenges are no longer just local or national, but often have a global dimension. In the following, we will present the most significant contemporary challenges in the field of public safety.

1. Cybercrime

In the digital age, cybercrime has become one of the biggest threats to public safety. "Increasing reliance on technology exposes individuals and institutions to unprecedented cyber risks, putting critical infrastructure and sensitive information at risk" (Smith, 2020, p. 14). With an increasing reliance on technology and the Internet, individuals, businesses and governments are becoming increasingly vulnerable to cyber attacks. Major challenges include:

- Ransomware attacks: Hackers encrypt data and demand rewards for unlocking it, affecting critical institutions such as hospitals, schools and government agencies. Miller Sarah explains that "ransomware is becoming increasingly sophisticated, targeting critical institutions and blocking access to vital information until a reward is paid" (Miller, 2019, p. 46).

- Identity theft and online fraud: These crimes affect millions of people globally, and protecting personal data is becoming a priority. "Online fraud and identity theft are among the most common forms of cybercrime, affecting individuals and companies alike" (Popescu, 2020, p. 72).

- Attacks on critical infrastructure: In an interconnected world, attacks on energy, financial or transportation systems can paralyze economic and social activities.

Preventing cybercrime and developing effective defense systems against attacks are major challenges for governments and organizations.

2. Terrorism and violent extremism

Terrorism remains a significant global threat to public safety. As Smith John states "direct terrorist attacks on the civilian population have been used as methods to induce fear and chaos, targeting crowded public spaces and state institutions" (Smith, 2018, p. 52). Extremist groups continue to pose a major risk, particularly through:

- Direct attacks on the population: These can take place in crowded public spaces or in state institutions, affecting both innocent citizens and structures of national importance.

- Online radicalization: The Internet and social media are often used to recruit new members to terrorist groups or to spread extremist ideologies. As Sarah Mil-

ler observes in "Digital Extremism and Online Radicalization," "online platforms are powerful tools in the hands of terrorist groups, facilitating the recruitment of young people and the rapid spread of extremist messages" (Miller, 2019, p. 34).

- Ideological struggles and domestic extremism: In many countries, violent extremism comes not only from external sources, but also from within local communities, fueling social tensions and conflicts. In this regard, Andrei Popescu notes that "internal radicalization, supported by economic and social tensions, represents a serious challenge for the internal stability of European states" (Popescu, 2020, p. 87).

Preventing and combating terrorism involves close international cooperation as well as strong domestic measures to prevent radicalization and rehabilitate individuals vulnerable to extremist ideologies.

3. Climate change and natural disasters

Climate change presents one of the greatest global challenges, with direct effects on public safety. "The frequency and intensity of natural disasters have increased significantly in recent decades, affecting billions of people and essential infrastructures" (Ionescu, 2020, p. 45). Extreme weather events such as hurricanes, wildfires, floods and severe droughts put pressure on emergency response systems and critical infrastructure.

Challenges include:

- Increasing frequency and intensity of natural disasters: "Extreme climatic phenomena, such as droughts and floods, endanger food security and water supply, which can trigger conflicts over limited resources" (Popescu Andreea, 2019, p. 78). These crises can generate international tensions and mass migrations.

- Massive population displacements: "Climate change is gradually transforming certain regions of the globe into uninhabitable areas, forcing millions of people to migrate, and this mass displacement brings significant pressure on the infrastructure and resources of the destination regions" (Dumitrescu Maria, 2021, p. 112).

Disaster management and climate change adaptation require a robust resilience plan and proactive measures to minimize long-term risks.

4. Organized crime

Organized crime continues to pose a major threat to public safety globally. "Cross-border criminal groups not only destabilize local economies, but also contribute to the spread of violence and corruption in public institutions" (Popescu, 2019, p. 34). These groups are involved in a range of illegal activities, including drug, arms and human trafficking.

Challenges include:

- Drug trafficking: "Drug cartels cause real social and economic crises, fueling a vicious circle of corruption and violence that undermines the authority of the state" (Ionescu Radu, 2020, p. 58). The destabilizing impact of these cartels is felt in many communities globally.

- Trafficking in human beings: "The exploitation of human beings is one of the cruelest and most

profitable activities of criminal groups, which take advantage of the economic and social vulnerabilities of the victims" (Dumitrescu Elena, 2018, p. 72). This form of crime seriously affects human rights and social order.

- Corruption and infiltration of state institutions: Criminal groups corrupt government institutions and legal systems, thereby undermining citizens' trust in law enforcement and state authority.

Combating organized crime requires strong international cooperation and rigorous law enforcement at the national level.

5. Public health crises

Pandemics and other public health crises pose a major challenge to public safety globally. "Pandemics like COVID-19 have highlighted the critical vulnerabilities of health systems, showing how quickly they can be overwhelmed by the massive demand for medical resources and services" (Popescu Andrei, 2021, p. 34). The COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated how vulnerable a society can be to rapidly spreading health threats.

Challenges include:

- Limited capacity of health systems: Pandemics can quickly overload health systems, putting pressure on limited resources and medical staff.

- Management of vaccines and medical resources: "The unequal distribution of vaccines during the pandemic accentuated social and economic disparities, underscoring the need for more equitable international policies in the distribution of medical resources" (Popescu Andrei, 2021, p. 58).

- Economic and social impact: Public health crises can have devastating effects on economies and social stability, affecting jobs, education systems and international relations.

To effectively manage these crises, governments must invest in the resilience of health systems and create robust pandemic management plans.

6. Migration and humanitarian crises

Forced migration due to conflict, economic crises or climate change is a major challenge to public safety globally. "Forced migration increases the risk of social destabilization in destination regions, especially when the number of migrants exceeds the absorption capacity of host societies" (Tical George, 2020, p. 45). While migration can be a positive phenomenon, when not managed properly, it can create social, economic and political tensions.

Challenges include:

- Refugee crises: Millions of people are forced to flee their homes due to war, persecution or natural disasters, putting pressure on the resources and infrastructure of host countries.

- Social and economic integration: The integration of migrants into the host society is often a difficult process, requiring effective policies and ample resources to prevent social exclusion and cultural conflicts.

- Illegal migration and human trafficking: "Organized crime networks take advantage of the vulnerability of illegal migrants, turning them into victims of

human trafficking or other forms of exploitation" (Tical George, 2020, p. 67).

Managing migration requires a global approach, with an emphasis on international cooperation, sustainable development and the protection of migrants' fundamental rights.

7. Food security and access to resources

Access to food and water is a growing problem in many regions of the world, especially in the context of climate change and armed conflict. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), "climate change will continue to adversely affect agriculture and food production, endangering global food security" (FAO, 2020). Food insecurity is also exacerbated by land degradation and extreme climatic conditions.

Food safety challenges include:

- Food insecurity: Climate change, drought and agricultural land degradation affect food production and access to food for millions of people.

- Wars and conflicts over resources: In many regions, conflicts over control of natural resources such as water or oil can lead to violence and instability. "Prolonged armed conflicts, especially in areas with limited natural resources, exacerbate food insecurity and contribute to humanitarian crises" (World Food Programme, 2021).

- Water crises: Lack of access to potable water and adequate irrigation resources is a critical problem in many parts of the world, generating forced migration and international tensions.

Managing natural resources in a sustainable and just way is essential to prevent conflict and ensure long-term stability.

Today's public safety challenges are diverse and complex, affecting all aspects of modern life, from health and the economy to the environment and national security. In the face of these threats, governments and societies must take a holistic and collaborative approach to protect citizens and ensure long-term stability. The ability to anticipate and respond effectively to contemporary challenges is critical to maintaining public safety in an increasingly unpredictable world.

7. The role of citizens in ensuring Public Safety

Public safety is not exclusively the responsibility of government institutions, but also of every citizen. In a modern society, citizens have a crucial role in crime prevention, actively involved in maintaining order and helping to reduce security risks. By promptly reporting crimes, obeying the law, and working closely with authorities, they can help create a safe and secure environment.

Civic education and risk awareness are essential for citizens to be prepared to respond to security challenges. By being actively involved in the community and adopting responsible behavior, they can make a significant contribution to maintaining public safety. The role of citizens is complemented by the activity of state institutions and has a direct impact on the creation of a safe and stable environment.

A primary way citizens support public safety is by promptly reporting suspicious activity or crime, thereby allowing authorities to intervene quickly and

prevent untoward events. Co-operation with the police, gendarmerie and other public order institutions is also essential, either by attending community meetings or assisting with investigations.

Participating in local crime prevention programs, such as neighborhood watches, helps reduce risk and creates a sense of safety. Adherence to laws and social norms is also crucial to maintaining order.

Another key element is education. Citizens can help prevent crime by informing themselves about cyber safety, preventing domestic violence or avoiding financial fraud. Involvement in community initiatives, such as clean-up campaigns or the rehabilitation of vulnerable areas, strengthens social cohesion and reduces crime.

In the digital age, citizens must play an active role in maintaining online safety by protecting personal data and avoiding the spread of false information. Also, their contribution to reducing social inequalities supports the stability of communities and prevents social unrest.

Citizen involvement in public safety is essential to creating a stable and safe society. From reporting crimes to active participation in the community, collaboration between citizens and authorities ensures a safe and harmonious living environment for all.

Conclusion

Public safety is a fundamental pillar of a society's stability and well-being. Its concept has evolved over time, becoming increasingly complex as new challenges and threats have emerged on the global landscape. Today, public safety includes not only protection against crime, but also ensuring economic stability, public health, cyber security and strong social cohesion.

Government institutions, from the police to local authorities, play a critical role in maintaining safety, but citizen involvement is equally important to the long-term success of policing efforts. In an increasingly interconnected and challenging world, cooperation between institutions and citizens becomes essential to face the complex challenges that threaten public safety.

The concept of public safety is vital to the functioning of any modern society. By protecting citizens, preventing unrest, and effectively managing crises, public safety supports stability, economic development, and trust in state institutions. In the absence of this concept, societies would become vulnerable to chaos, violence and poverty, compromising overall well-being and progress.

References:

1. The Constitution of Romania, republished, amended and supplemented by Law on the revision of the Constitution of Romania no. 429/2003;
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3. Law no. 218/2002 regarding the organization and functioning of the Romanian Police;

4. Law no. 550/2004 regarding the organization and operation of the Romanian Gendarmerie;

5. Law no. 51/1991 on Romania's national security, republished in 2014;

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